

Research Station Canning, West Bengal. The trial was in a randomized block design replicated 3 times in a 1-m-deep plot. All 30 entries were sown 22 Jun 1984 and transplanted on 23 Aug. Each entry was transplanted in 4 rows, at 30 hills/row. Spacing between rows and plants was 30 cm. Standing water depth at transplanting was 12 cm and surface soil (0-15 cm) salinity (EC_{sw}) in situ was 9.0 dS/m. Standing water depth during

crop growth was 29-58 cm in Aug, 47-50 cm in Sep, 41-51 cm in Oct, and 38 cm in Nov and Dec. The crop was harvested in Jan 1985.

Survival rate of the plants that survived to maturity ranged from 4 to 95% (see table). RPAR7360 and PLAI 100 did not survive. NC540 had maximum survival of 95%, followed by NC491 with 91%. Panicles/ m^2 ranged from 47 to 142, with NC492 producing

the most. CR292-5258 produced 135 panicles/ m^2 , but it also exhibited maximum spikelet sterility (77.6%). Kalamota (sel) had 68% survival and 105 panicles/ m^2 , whereas Pankaj had a survival rate of 68% and produced 75 panicles/ m^2 . The three highest yielding entries were NC491, 780 g/plot; SR26B, 743 g/plot; and NC487/77, 490 g/plot. Local check Kalamota (sel) yielded 392 g/plot. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Utilization of wide compatibility gene (S_5^n) for rice breeding

H. Araki, K. Toya, and H. Ikehashi.
Tropical Agriculture Research Center,
Okinawa, Japan

F₁ hybrids of indica-japonica crosses show semisterility, while some wide compatibility varieties (WCVs) produce fertile F₁ plants when crossed with indica or with japonica varieties. We analyzed the genetic base for F₁ sterility and wide compatibility as follows. A set of multiple alleles was located between the *C* (chromogen for apiculus color) and *wx* (waxy endosperm) loci; S_5^n for WCVs, S_5^i for indica varieties, and S_5^j for japonica varieties, and the genotypes of S_5^n/S_5^i and S_5^n/S_5^j were fertile, but S_5^i/S_5^j was semisterile because of partial abortion of gametes carrying S_5^j . So far, some javanicas or derivatives such as Ketan Nangka, Calotoc, and CPSLO 17 have been found to possess S_5^n , and they also have the complementary genes for apiculus color, i.e. C^+ and A^+ . Since C^+ is closely linked with S_5^n , the progeny of indica/ WCVs or japonica/ WCVs showing apiculus color are likely to possess S_5^n .

We have selected several lines from Ketan Nangka (KN) crosses. The progeny of IR50//IR36/ Ketan Nangka showed indica-like plant type as well as good fertility of F₁ when crossed with japonica testers (see table). Likewise, some lines selected from

Characteristics of some promising lines with wide compatibility gene S_5^n , 1986.

Line	Cross or variety	Generation	Flowering date	Plant ht (cm)	F ₁ fertility	
					Tester	Fertility (%)
A1	Akihikari/NK4 ^a	F ₅	20 May	94	IR50	89.4
A9	Akihikari/NK4	F ₅	22 May	87	IR50	85.4
B5	Akihikari//Akihikari/NK4	F ₄	20 May	80	IR36	90.7
B20	Akihikari//Akihikari/NK4	F ₄	18 May	92	IR36	86.9
C1	IR50//IR36/Ketan Nangka	F ₅	29 May	92	Akihikari	83.5
C2	IR50//IR36/Ketan Nangka	F ₅	29 May	98	Akihikari	90.3
	Ketan Nangka		15 Jun	158	IR36	88.2
	Toyonishiki (check)		21 May	88	Akihikari	93.4
	IR36 (check)		4 Jun	81		89.1
	IR50/Akihikari F ₁ (check)		(test in 1983)			42.8

^a NK4 is an F₆ line from Nihonmasari/Ketan Nangka.

Akihikari//Akihikari/ (a line from Nihonmasari/ Ketan Nangka) showed normal F₁ fertility when crossed with IR36, although the lines are morphologically japonica type (see table).

The incorporation of S_5^n gene to indica or japonica breeding lines is expected to alleviate the sterility problem in indica-japonica crosses.

Specifically, those lines with S_5^n can be used for hybrid seed production, inasmuch as they would reveal high level of heterosis without F₁ sterility. As some IR varieties, including IR36 and IR50, possess a restorer gene for cytoplasmic male sterility of japonica type, indica-like lines with the S_5^n can be used directly as parents for hybrid seed production. *ℓ*

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

Etiology of rice orange leaf

H. Hibino, G.B. Jonson, and F.C. Sta. Cruz,
Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

In Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia, orange leaf is known to be associated

with mycoplasma-like organisms (MLO). Recent reports from China indicated that virus-like particles are associated with orange leaf.

We collected 34 rice plants with orange leaf-like symptoms from 6 Philippine sites. *Recilia dorsalis* nymphs

were allowed to feed on each plant for 2 and 4 d, and then were transferred to healthy 7- to 10-d-old TN1 seedlings at 1 insect/seedling, where they remained until they died.

An average 13% of the insects transmitted the disease agent. Incubation period was 15-33 d. About 10% of the infective insects could transmit the disease agent until they died. Disease agent retention was 18-43 d. Incubation period in plants was 10-28 d. In addition to orange leaf symptoms, young leaves of inoculated seedlings

Electron micrograph of MLO in a sieve tube of rice leaves infected with orange leaf (20,000X).

were ragged and twisted. Infected seedlings died 3-4 wk after symptoms appeared.

Under the electron microscope, ultrathin sections of leaf tissue from plants infected with each isolate showed MLO in the sieve tubes. The MLO were bounded by a unit membrane and a pleomorphic 50-1100 nm in diameter (see figure), which indicates that the pathogen causing orange leaf in the Philippines is not a virus and is most likely a MLO. *S*

Tungro (RTV) incidence in Andhra Pradesh in 1984

A. Ghosh and A.P.R. Reddy, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

RTV is a major problem in India. Since 1970, it has been recorded in Oct-Nov in

isolated areas of Andhra Pradesh. In 1984 rabi and kharif it reached epidemic proportions (Table 1). Except for IR50, most varieties grown in Andhra Pradesh are susceptible.

Disease surveys were conducted in Ranga Reddy, Medak, Karim Nagar, West Godavari, Guntur, Prakasam, Nellore, and Chittoor Districts from Jan

to Nov 1984. Field diagnosis used visual symptoms and the IRRRI iodine test. Transmission tests were conducted on all samples with positive iodine tests. Selected virus isolates from TN1 were evaluated in serodiagnostic tests using antisera from IRRRI. The tests confirmed that the disease was RTV (Table 2). *S*

Table 1. RTV-affected areas in Andhra Pradesh in 1984.

District	Months	Varieties affected	Area affected (ha)	Severity
Ranga Reddy	Jan-Feb	Tellahamsa	8,000	Severe
Medak	Mar	Tellahamsa	1,500	do-
Karim Nagar	Mar	Tellahamsa	1,500	Moderate-severe
West Godavari	Jan-Feb	BPT1235	5,000	do-
Nellore	May-Jun	IET2508	3,000	do-
Chittoor	Jun-Jul	Rasi	5,000	Severe
		IET2508		
Prakasam	Oct-Nov	NLR9674	15,000	do-
		MTU9029		
Guntur	Oct-Nov	NLR9674	15,000	do-

Table 2. RTV incidence^a in rice varieties grown in RTV epidemic areas during 1984.

District	Variety	Planting date	RTV incidence (visual)	Iodine test	Transmission	GLH population
Medak	Tellahamsa	Oct 1983	H	+	+	M
	RNR1446	Nov 1983	H	+	+	M
	IR50	Nov 1983	L	-	-	-
Ranga Reddy	Tellahamsa	Nov-Dec 1983	H	+	+	M
Nellore	IET2508	Mar 1984	H	+	+	M
	Rasi	Mar 1984	H	+	+	H
	IR50	Mar 1984	L	-	-	L
	NLR9672	Aug 1984	H	+	+	M
Prakasam	NLR9674	Aug 1984	H	+	+	M
Chittoor	Rasi	May-Jun 1984	M	+	+	M
	IET2508	May-Jun 1984	M	+	+	M
	IR50	May-Jun 1984	-	-	-	-
	RGL 2624	Jun 1984	M	+	+	M

^a L = low, M = moderate, H = high.

Granular fungicides for controlling blast (BI)

H.D. Lewin, V. Mariappan, and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

Bl caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is increasing in Tamil Nadu. Foliar fungicides are advocated for disease control. Sometimes, however, lack of sprayers prevents proper spray application. Granular fungicides require no special equipment. Soil-applied granular fungicides are absorbed by roots and systemic action protects rice stems, nodes, panicles, and foliage. Granular fungicides require fewer applications and less labor to apply than do sprays.

We evaluated probenazol (Oryzemat 8G), pyroquilon (Coratop 5G), chlorbenthiazole (S. 1901 6G), and IBP (Kitazin 17G) for BI control. Highly BI-susceptible IR50 was planted in Oct-Jan 1984-85 in a randomized block design with four replications.

Fungicides were applied at tillering and panicle initiation at 30 and 40 kg formulated product/ha. IBP, which has a much higher active ingredient content